

Supplemental material for research article by Pals et al., “Reservoirs and proposed transmission routes of *Staphylococcus aureus* related to intramammary infections in dairy goats: A scoping review”, published in Journal of Dairy Science.

Table 2. Search strings used in the tailored search for supporting literature for the transmission routes, discussion and knowledge gaps.

Keywords	Database used the timeslot between 08-07-2025 and 15-12-2025	No. hits screened for title and/or abstract	Publications used
Within goat transmission – internal			
Overcome host defense AND <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> AND nasal carriage	PubMed All Fields	2	Sakr et al., 2018
Mastitis AND blood AND milk AND barrier AND review	PubMed All Fields	19	Wellnitz & Bruckmaier, 2021
Subclinical AND mastitis AND dairy AND goats AND udder half AND infection	Scopus title.abstract.keywords	31	Koop et al., 2013
Within goat transmission – external			
Self-suckling AND behavior AND goat	Scopus title.abstract.keywords	2	O’Brien, 1982
Self-suckling AND behavior AND goat	PubMed All Fields	2	Martínez-de la Puente et al., 2011
Transmission between goats – Indirect			
Transmission AND dairy AND <i>staphylococcus aureus</i> AND milking AND machine	PubMed All Fields	7	Deng et al., 2021
Mastitis AND management AND prevention AND transmission AND <i>staphylococcus aureus</i>	Scopus title.abstract.keywords	19	Ruegg, 2017
Mastitis AND <i>staphylococcus aureus</i> AND teatcup	Scopus title.abstract.keywords	4	Michael et al., 2021
Reverse pressure AND milking AND cows	Scopus title.abstract.keywords	4	Rasmussen et al., 1994
Udder asymmetry AND goat	Scopus title.abstract.keywords	15	de Geus et al., 2023
Survival AND <i>staphylococcus aureus</i> AND dust	Scopus title.abstract.keywords	23	White et al., 2020 Feld et al., 2018
Transmission between goats – direct			
Intersuckling	Scopus title.abstract.keywords	18	Keil et al., 2001
Discussion and knowledge gaps			
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> AND dairy AND cows AND colonization AND extramammary	PubMed All Fields	2	Exel et al., 2023
Bovine AND <i>staphylococcus aureus</i> AND nasal carriage	PubMed All Fields	35	Nemeghaire et al., 2014
Found during systematic search	Cab Abstracts		Romanò et al., 2020
Airborne AND <i>staphylococcus aureus</i> AND swine	PubMed All Fields	25	Angen et al., 2021
Electrostatic dust collector AND pig farms	PubMed All Fields	10	Rittscher et al., 2023
Udder hygiene AND milking	PubMed All Fields	31	Pankey et al., 1989
Clonal diversity AND <i>staphylococcus aureus</i> AND goat	PubMed All Fields	16	Porro et al., 2011